

Development and Review Processes for DDI Standards and Official Technical Documents

DDI Technical Committee
Version 2: February 2023

The Data Documentation Initiative (DDI) Alliance develops specification and technical products supporting the documentation, management, and integration of social science data and other data about human activity. Examples of specification products (published and under development) include DDI-Codebook, DDI-Lifecycle, XKOS, SDTL, DISCO, and DDI-CDI. Examples of technical products include DDI Controlled Vocabularies.

Official Technical Documents are those that are published by the DDI working groups responsible for the development and maintenance of a product within the DDI Product Suite. These include:

- High level documentation (not published as part of the specification package and subject to publication through the product versioning process)
- Best Practices
- Implementation Guides

The development and review process passes through a number of specific groups:

Scientific Board: responsible for determining overall direction of the DDI product suite and establishing working groups within the DDI Alliance

Technical Committee: responsible for managing the development, review, and publication of DDI products

Scientific Community: responsible for contributing to the content, development, and review of DDI products and voting, through the Designated Member Representative, for the publication of new products and revision of existing products

Working Groups: established by the Scientific Board, working groups have specific responsibilities defined at the time of their establishment. The two types of working groups involved in product development are product-specific working groups and content working groups.

Workflow Summary

1.0 Initiating new product or new content

1.1 New product proposal

1.2 Requesting changes to existing products

2.0 Process for approval of new products or product versions

2.1 Technical review

2.2 Public review

2.3 Scientific community vote

2.4 Publication of the approved product version

2.5 Disposal of development work that does not result in publication

1.0 Initiating New Content and/or New Product

1.1 New Product Proposal

Proposals for new standards or technical products may result in the creation of new working groups of the DDI Alliance. To help the community effectively review and assess the proposal, the proposal must include:

- a complete draft statement of content and functionality
- information about the business case for the proposed product
- the objectives the new product will achieve
- position within the suite of products supported by the DDI Alliance
- identification of a core group to work on the development of the product
- a maintenance plan

The proposal will be presented to the Scientific Board for approval and creation of a Working Group. Approval will require the determination of the fit of the new content area within the Scientific Plan. This review could result in the expansion of the Scientific Plan. Once approved the new proposed product would be developed along the same lines as changes to any current products including close coordination with the Technical Committee.

ACTON: Interested group submits a proposal for the development of a new product to the Scientific Board

ACTION: Scientific Board evaluates the request and establishes a product development

working group if accepted.

1.2 Requesting New Content Coverage

New content coverage is defined as content that is not currently addressed by DDI. This could be coverage for a new disciplinary area requiring specialized content to capture processes or related data. For example, expanding coverage to include qualitative data or paradata. A proposal for new content should reflect the input of the DDI community concerned with the topic area. To help the community assess the proposal during review, the proposal must include:

- a complete draft statement of content and functionality
- information about the business case for the proposed change
- the objectives that the added content will achieve.

Where the new content requires the creation of a new Working Group, the proposal will be presented to the Scientific Board for approval. New content would require a new working if the content significantly expands the coverage of one or more DDI products. It does not include enhancements to existing coverage areas. New content working groups should be established if the content may be applicable to multiple products so that a common conceptual model is developed that can be expressed as needed in different products.

Once approved, the Working Group proposing the expansion should coordinate work with the Technical Committee to develop the proposed addition within the product's development framework, which allows for iterative testing of the model. To be reviewed for eventual merging within a project, the final proposal should provide:

- a revised model with object level documentation
- high level documentation regarding how the new coverage meets the requirements of the underlying use cases (including examples where relevant)
- recommendation as to the products which could/should include the new coverage area

The Technical Committee will review this content and in collaboration with the Scientific Board make a recommendation to the product groups regarding their inclusion of the new content area in their product. Development and review of the new product version including this content follows the standard version process.

The Technical Committee may determine that the new content should result in a new product in the DDI Product Suite. This recommendation will be coordinated with the topical working group and presented to the Scientific Board to determine its fit within the Scientific Work Plan.

ACTION: Submission of content coverage expansion to the Scientific Board

ACTION: Review by Technical Committee resulting in a recommendation to the Scientific Board

ACTION: Scientific Board evaluates request and declines or accepts the proposal. Declined proposals can be resubmitted with additional information. Accepted proposals should result in the establishment of a content working group to develop the parameters of the new content coverage, identify requirements, and draft a model of required information objects and relationships.

1.3 Requesting Changes to Existing Products

Anyone, including non-members of the DDI Alliance, may request corrections or expansions to DDI specification or technical products. Corrections or extensions of current content should be recorded in the issue tracker of the specified product. They will be handled by the product working group responsible for the development and/or maintenance of the product. This working group will determine the timeline for addressing the issue.

Each product group will provide clear directions on how to request changes (for example, link to issue tracker, submitting by email, etc.). These directions will be provided on each product page at the DDI Alliance Site. Each page will also indicate that if the user is unsure which product(s) the change should apply to they may also submit the request to the Technical Committee issue tracker and it will be reviewed and relayed to the appropriate product group(s).

2.0 Process for Approval of New Products or Product Versions

2.1 Technical Review

The Technical Review of new content is performed iteratively during development. The extent of technical review varies by the complexity of the change in the model. Each Technical Review should specify its scope and goals (limited section, comprehensive, version type verification, etc.). The Technical Review should include members of the DDI community familiar with the product as well as the usage needs addressed by the change. The Technical Review is to confirm the level of change (see below), verify that the modeling and design standards of the product are followed, and evaluate the success of the change in addressing the issue or need it is intended to address. Each product follows its own versioning line which adheres to Semantic Versioning (semver.org) guidelines. Completion of a Technical Review occurs when the goals have been achieved.

Patches (backward compatible bug fix) require a Technical Review by the Technical Committee. A Patch may be implemented immediately following a Technical Review, without requiring a Public Review and Scientific Community Vote.

Minor Version changes functional additions to the current content that are backward compatible (example: relaxing cardinality, documentation addition, additional parameters, etc.) A Technical Review is required addressing the specifics of the changes made.

Major Version changes result in incompatible API changes. These involve a Technical Review addressing each specific area of change.

2.2 Public Review

Public Reviews are managed by the Technical Committee. After Technical Review, the proposal is posted for a Public Review of at least one month. A Patch does not require a Public Review. The package for a Public Review must include:

- Revised model with complete object level documentation
- High level documentation and examples where appropriate
- Change log

- Report on the results of the Technical Review

The Executive Director will distribute the revised specification to the public, primarily by posting on the public website and announcing the review to the relevant communities. All public comments will be published and openly available. Any issues raised during this Public Review must be publicly answered by the Technical Committee. The period of Public Review may be extended at the discretion of the proposal Lead, the Technical Committee, or the Executive Director.

2.3 Membership Vote

As outlined above, the Membership may be called to vote at a number of stages in the development of DDI Alliance Standards. The Technical Committee initiates the Membership Vote which is managed by the Secretariat.

Each Member Organization has one vote which is cast by their Designated Member Representative. Associate Member Organizations do not have voting rights.

Minor Version Changes and Major Version Changes require a vote. Patch Version Changes do not require a vote.

Each Designated Member Representative member is asked to provide a "Yes" or "No" vote. The period of the vote shall be no less than one month.

The DDI Alliance strives for consensus, justifying its decisions and interpretations in terms of principle and of empirical practice. As our product suite grows we recognize that some products may have a more targeted audience within the DDI Membership. These voting practices reflect the greater need for full community buy-in when adding a new product to the product suite.

Voting requirements:

At least 35% of the membership needs to participate in the voting process.

Approval requires the following percentage of VOTES CAST: 50%=> YES votes cast. If less than 35% of the membership participates in the vote AND the criteria for approval is met, the Scientific Board can decide to abide by the result of the votes cast and approve the new version.

All decisions, or the direct vote or further deliberation of the Scientific Board will be announced by the Executive Director.

2.4 Publication of the Approved Version Change

If the product change is rejected, the comments and decision are referred back to the product development group. The group will determine whether there should be additional work done based on the comments or if the work should be tabled.

If accepted, the Technical Committee will manage the incorporation of corrections noted in the

Public Review and prepare the new version of the specification or technical product for publication. This will include a revised model, a technical implementation, appropriate documentation as a usable guide, and revised high-level technical documentation. The Technical Committee will review corrections with the Executive Director to determine if an additional review period is needed. Timing of publication is dependent upon resources and will be determined by the Executive Director in consultation with the Technical Committee.

2.5 Disposal of Development Work that Does Not Result in Publication

2.5.1 No Proposal for Publication

If a working group does not complete its work in preparation for publication the content of their work will be documented and archived for possible future development. The Scientific Board will follow its guidelines for the dissolution or re-constitution of working groups. This work continues to be considered as under development.

2.5.2 Failed Review or Vote for Publication

If interest in the working group continues the Technical Committee will work with the product development working group to address the issues raised in review or vote for publication. A review of the standards landscape should be made to determine the continued relevance of the product. The Technical Committee will make a recommendation to the Scientific Board regarding the continuance of the working group. The Scientific Board will follow its guidelines in determining the status of the working group.

2.5.3 Cancellation of Development Work

Any Working Group may, at any point during product development work, raise issues of concern to the Scientific Board. This would normally occur only in situations where a working group has stopped meeting or making progress over a period of some time, or if the standard environment changes significantly making the product a poor fit for the DDI Product Suite. For example, if other products have been created which address the need which the proposed product was designed to meet. The decision regarding the cancellation of development work resides with the Scientific Board.

3.0 Review Process for Official Technical Documents

Official Technical Documents are those that are published by the DDI working groups responsible for the development and maintenance of a product within the DDI Product Suite. High-level documentation is separate from the product package and is not covered by the product versioning process in terms of publication. The intent is to allow modification and revision of these official documents in a separate process that will ensure adequate review of timely updates and improvements. , Best Practices, Implementation Guides, etc. are the type of documents being discussed in this section.

Official documents of this type should receive some level of review to ensure that they are comprehensive, accurate and understandable. This may require several levels of review. This document recommends a standard approach to ensure this level of quality.

Note that the purpose of these reviews is to obtain feedback on the accuracy and readability of the document. Lack of response should not delay publication. The following steps are intended to provide guidance to the working groups to ensure that they provide the opportunity for appropriate feedback on new technical documents. The product group is responsible for responding to all review comments and modifying the document as needed to address these comments. Time guidelines are based on past experience. Expert review may be provided as the document is developed through the involvement of a broad community. The point is to provide the opportunity for comment by key communities and to improve the quality of the document.

3.1 Types of review:

3.1.1 Expert Review

This review should address the coverage of the document and its technical quality. It should involve bringing in technical experts (other product groups, implementers, etc.) who are able to evaluate the accuracy and appropriateness of the content. Coverage should be evaluated on both whether the document covers the stated content and whether additional content should be added for clarification and practical usage. Comments received during the review should be noted and addressed. These may or may not result in changes to the content.

3.1.2 Comprehension Review

This review should address the ability of the intended audience to understand the content and intended application of the document. This should involve the identification of new glossary terms, comprehension, and language level. The product group should notify other working groups of the comprehension review so they can comment if they wish. This should be considered a general public review targeted at the intended audience. Comments received during the review should be noted and addressed. These may or may not result in changes to the content.

3.2 Recommended Process:

The time frames noted below are guidelines and may be shorter or longer depending on the specific document.

3.2.1 Preparation:

Process

This is an internal process and will vary by group and document type. The group should be large enough to provide various perspectives and include both group members and any additional experts identified by the group. Timeline should reflect both the need for the document and availability of members to work on the document.

Review

Internal review by working group members. Verify that intended coverage is clear and the content meets the intent of the group.

Timeframe

No specific time frame recommended.

3.2.2 Expert Review:**Process**

The product group in consultation with the Technical Committee will identify groups to involve in the expert review. Distribute and provide a means of responding to the document, identifying suggested changes, and making recommendations.

Review

Review of technical aspects of the document. Coverage and technical accuracy are the focus of this review. Note that the Technical Committee can help provide options for collecting comments.

Timeframe

A review time of 4-6 weeks is recommended. Individual documents may vary from this recommendation.

Incorporation of Comments

Substantive changes to the reviewed document may result in a subsequent review.

3.2.3 Comprehension Review:**Preparation**

This should include a specific request for involvement from the appropriate DDI working groups, as needed. The comprehension review should include requests for review by the intended audiences for the document.

Review

Focus of review is comprehension of content and diagrams. Reviewers should have a clear means of providing feedback. Note that the Technical Committee can help provide options for collecting comments.

Timeframe

A review time of 6-8 weeks is recommended. Individual documents may vary from this recommendation. Based on experience, a minimum of 4 weeks is generally required to obtain a response.

Incorporation of Comments

Substantive changes to the reviewed document may result in a subsequent review.

3.3 Publication

Once any changes based on review comments have been incorporated and the document is finalized, the publication on the Product page is handled by the Technical Committee. To publish your Technical Document:

1. Provide the Technical Committee with a copy of the PDF document or content link to an HTML publication
2. Provide a short summary of the document that will inform the user of the coverage of the document (this will be associated with the link on the product page)
3. The Technical Committee will discuss the appropriate posting for the document with the working group
4. The Technical Committee will post the document description and link on the product page and inform the Marketing Committee of the new document so that it can be appropriately publicized
5. Any questions regarding the publication process should be addressed to the Technical Committee